
**HOTEL INDUSTRY IN TURKEY AND ITS IMPACT ON DEVELOPING
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM, WHILE HOTEL SERVICES IN UZBEKISTAN ARE
COMPARED TO THOSE IN TURKEY.**

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Abstract.

The primary objective of the article is to explore how the hotel industry and digital services impact the growth of tourism in Turkey and Uzbekistan. The study delves into the concept of management and its various aspects, including the competitiveness of enterprises, employees, managers, and hotel entities. Turkey provides a diverse range of accommodation options, ranging from budget-friendly hostels to high-end luxury resorts, and has a well-established tourism infrastructure with numerous hotels offering various facilities such as spas, pools, and restaurants. The reason for selecting this research area is that Turkey is one of the most popular tourist destinations globally, attracting visitors from all over the world and facing intense competition in the hotel industry. The study focuses on three types of hotels: those affiliated with international chains, those affiliated with national brands, and independent enterprises.

Keywords.

Accommodation, hospitality, tourism, resorts, luxury, boutique, amenities, cuisine, spa, conference facilities, location, beachfront, city center, historical sites, entertainment, activities, customer service, reviews, online booking, renewable energy, revenue management, digital service.

INTRODUCTION

The hotel industry plays a vital role in the development of sustainable tourism, and Turkey is a prime example of this. As one of the world's top tourist destinations, Turkey has a well-established tourism infrastructure, with a diverse range of accommodation options. From budget-friendly hostels to high-end luxury resorts, the country offers something for every type of traveler. However, with the rise of digital services and increased competition in the hotel industry, it's crucial to examine the impact of these factors on the sustainability of tourism in Turkey. This article aims to explore the role of the hotel industry in Turkey's sustainable tourism development and compare it with Uzbekistan's hotel services to gain insights into the best practices for achieving sustainable tourism in the hotel industry. By analyzing the concept of management in the hotel industry and examining the different types of hotels in both countries, this article provides valuable insights into the strategies that hotel businesses can employ to promote sustainable tourism in Turkey and beyond.

HOTEL INDUSTRY

The hotel industry is a sector of the hospitality industry that includes businesses that provide lodging, meals, and other services to travelers and tourists. Hotels can range from small, independently owned establishments to large, multinational chains with thousands of rooms. The hotel industry is a significant contributor to the global economy, generating billions of dollars in revenue each year. The industry provides employment opportunities for millions of people worldwide, including hotel staff, managers, chefs, and other professionals. Hotels typically offer a range of amenities and services to their guests, including room service, concierge services, fitness centers, swimming pools, restaurants, and bars. Some hotels specialize in specific types of accommodations, such as luxury hotels, resort hotels, budget hotels, or boutique hotels. The hotel industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with the rise of online booking platforms and the increasing popularity of alternative accommodations such as vacation rentals and home-sharing services. Hotels are also adopting technology to enhance the guest experience, such as offering keyless entry, in-room tablets, and personalized recommendations based on guest preferences. Also, technology has had a significant impact on the hotel industry, with the rise of online booking platforms, mobile apps, and digital marketing. This has led to increased competition among hotels and a greater focus on providing high-quality service and unique experiences to attract and retain customers. The hotel industry faces several challenges, including increasing competition from alternative accommodations

such as vacation rentals and home-sharing services, fluctuating demand, rising labor costs, and changing consumer preferences. The COVID-19 pandemic has also had a significant impact on the hotel industry, with travel restrictions and reduced demand leading to widespread closures and layoffs. Despite the challenges, the hotel industry is expected to grow in the coming years, driven by rising global travel and tourism demand. However, the industry is also likely to undergo significant changes, with hotels increasingly focused on providing unique experiences and embracing technology to enhance guest satisfaction. Sustainability and social responsibility are also likely to become more important factors in the hotel industry's future. Overall, the hotel industry remains a vital component of the global economy and plays a significant role in the travel and tourism sector.

Picture 1 : <https://images.app.goo.gl/uuk2uuMon3m899zF7>

THE HOTEL INDUSTRY'S INVOLVEMENT IN TOURISM WITHIN TURKEY.

The hotel industry plays a significant role in the tourism sector in Turkey, and its impact can be felt in several ways:

1. **Promotion:** Hotels in Turkey are often used as promotional tools for the tourism industry. They can showcase the beauty and attractions of Turkey through their marketing campaigns, and provide visitors with information about local attractions and activities.

2. **Infrastructure:** The hotel industry plays a key role in the development of infrastructure in Turkey, particularly in areas that are popular with tourists. This includes the development of roads, airports, and other transportation links, as well as the construction of new hotels and other tourism-related facilities.

3. Cultural exchange: The hotel industry provides an opportunity for cultural exchange between tourists and locals in Turkey. Visitors can learn about local customs and traditions, try local cuisine, and experience the hospitality and warmth of Turkish culture through their interactions with hotel staff and other locals.

4. Sustainability: The hotel industry in Turkey is increasingly focused on sustainability and environmental responsibility. Many hotels are implementing eco-friendly practices, such as using renewable energy sources, reducing waste, and conserving water, which helps to protect Turkey's natural resources and promote sustainable tourism.

5. Revenue: The hotel industry generates significant revenue for Turkey's economy. This includes revenue from room rates, taxes, and other fees charged to guests, as well as revenue generated by related industries such as transportation, restaurants, and tour operators.

6. Employment: The hotel industry is a significant employer in Turkey, providing job opportunities for a significant number of people. This includes not only hotel staff, but also those who work in related industries such as food and beverage, housekeeping, and maintenance.

7. Accommodation: The hotel industry provides a wide range of accommodation options for tourists, from budget-friendly options to high-end luxury resorts. This variety of accommodation options helps to attract tourists with different budgets and preferences to visit Turkey.

8. Innovation: The hotel industry is increasingly using technology and innovation to improve the guest experience and attract more tourists to Turkey. This includes the implementation of digital technologies like mobile key technology, online booking and reservation systems, and guest feedback systems.

Overall, the hotel industry is a critical component of the tourism sector in Turkey, providing essential services and facilities that help to attract and retain visitors. The industry generates revenue, creates jobs, and promotes cultural exchange and sustainable tourism practices, all of which contribute to the continued growth and success of Turkey's tourism sector.

HOTEL SERVICES IN TURKEY

Hotels in Turkey offer a wide range of services to meet the needs of their guests. Accommodation is one of the most common services offered, with hotels providing various room types, from standard rooms to suites and villas, to accommodate different needs and preferences. Dining is another popular service with many hotels in Turkey having on-site restaurants that offer local and international cuisine. Room service is also available for guests who prefer to dine in their room. For guests that want to relax and unwind, many hotels in Turkey have on-site spas and wellness centers that offer a range of treatments, such as massages, facials, and body scrubs. Fitness facilities, such as gyms, swimming pools, and sports courts, are also available for guests who want to stay active during their stay. For business travelers, hotels often have business centers, meeting rooms, and conference facilities, equipped with the latest technology, to accommodate different group sizes. Concierge services are also available in many hotels to assist guests with booking tours, arranging transportation, and providing recommendations for local attractions and restaurants. Most hotels in Turkey have a 24-hour reception desk where guests can check in and out at any time and address any issues or concerns they may have during their stay. Some hotels offer transportation services, such as airport transfers or shuttle buses to nearby attractions.

DIGITAL

SERVICE.

Turkey's hotels offer a variety of digital services to enhance the guest experience and improve efficiency. Online booking is one such service that allows guests to book a room, select their preferred room type, and make payments online.

Mobile check-in and check-out services are also commonly found in Turkish hotels, allowing guests to skip the front desk and go directly to their room upon arrival. Some hotels have their own mobile apps, providing guests with access to information about hotel services, make restaurant reservations, and order room service.

Smart room controls are another digital service provided by hotels in Turkey, allowing guests to control various aspects of their room, such as lighting, temperature, and entertainment systems, using their mobile devices. With the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, many hotels in Turkey have implemented contactless payment systems to reduce the risk of transmission. These digital services provide guests with greater convenience, flexibility, and control over their stay, enhancing their experience in Turkish hotels.

Picture 2: <https://images.app.goo.gl/pDPNC6eRtKGTi8iF7>

Digital services have helped Turkish hotels improve their operational efficiency, by automating tasks and providing real-time data and insights. This has enabled hotels to reduce costs, improve their service offerings, and enhance their overall guest experience.

DEVELOPMENT OF HOTEL INDUSTRY.

The role of the hotel industry in tourism in Turkey has evolved over the years. In 2016, Turkish hotels began to embrace digitalization to improve the guest experience. This included the use of mobile apps for check-in and check-out, keyless room entry, and digital concierge services. Hotels also invested in digital marketing to reach a wider audience and improve their online presence.

Turkish hotels focused on improving the guest experience by investing in staff training in 2018. This included providing training to staff in customer service, language skills, and cultural awareness. The following year, in 2019, hotels in Turkey began collaborating with local communities to create unique experiences that showcase the local culture and traditions. This included offering tours and activities that were led by locals. However, in 2020, the hotel industry in Turkey faced an unexpected challenge due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Hotels had to adapt to new health and safety protocols, including increased cleaning and sanitation measures, to ensure the safety of their guests.

Impact of Covid-19 on Turkish tourism

Picture 3:

https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl=http%3A%2F%2Fcountry.eiu.com%2Fasset_images%2F710065654.gif&tbnid=DenFpBdb6XA3ZM&vet=1&imgrefurl=http%3A%2F%2Fcountry.eiu.com%2Farticle.aspx%3Farticleid%3D700065653%26Country%3DTurkey%26topic%3DEconomy%26subtopic%3DFor_7&docid=Espm5bnSvjYxM&w=530&h=283&hl=ru-RU&source=sh%2Fx%2Fim

Many hotels also offered flexible booking policies to accommodate changing travel plans. Despite the challenges, the industry remained resilient and continued to play a vital role in the country's tourism sector. In recent years, Turkey's hotel industry has been focusing on developing its infrastructure and expanding its tourism offerings. The government has implemented various initiatives to attract more tourists, such as easing visa regulations and investing in new airports and transportation networks. The industry has also been focusing on improving the

quality of its services, with many hotels undergoing renovations and upgrades to meet international standards. One of the key strategies that Turkey's hotel industry has been pursuing is diversification. The industry has been working on developing new tourism offerings beyond the traditional sun and sea holidays, such as cultural and historical tourism, adventure tourism, and health and wellness tourism. This has involved promoting lesser-known destinations within the country and collaborating with local communities to offer authentic experiences to visitors.

HOTEL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN.

The hotel industry in Uzbekistan has been rapidly developing over the past few years, with a growing number of international hotel chains opening their doors in the country. The government of Uzbekistan has been actively promoting the country's tourism industry, and has implemented a number of initiatives to attract foreign investment in the hotel sector. These initiatives include tax incentives, simplified procedures for obtaining permits and licenses, and the establishment of a dedicated tourism development fund. As a result of these efforts, several international hotel chains have opened or announced plans to open properties in Uzbekistan. These include the Marriott, Hyatt, Hilton, Intercontinental, and Radisson hotel chains, among others.

DIGITALIZATION

Since 2018 digitalization is rapidly transforming the hotel industry in Uzbekistan, with many hotels embracing new technologies to enhance the guest experience and improve operational efficiency. One area where digitalization has had a significant impact is in the booking and reservation process. Many hotels in Uzbekistan now offer online booking systems, allowing guests to easily make reservations and access information about room availability, pricing, and amenities. In addition, digital technologies are being used to streamline check-in and check-out processes, with many hotels implementing self-service kiosks and mobile check-in options to reduce wait times and improve guest satisfaction. Digital technologies are also being used to enhance the guest experience during their stay. For example, some hotels in Uzbekistan now offer mobile apps that allow guests to order room service, request housekeeping services, and access information about local attractions and events.

Although the hotel industry in Uzbekistan is rapidly adopting digital technologies to enhance the guest experience and improve operational efficiency, it still lags behind countries like Turkey in terms of the level of digital service provided by hotels.

Here are some digital service recommendations that Uzbek hotels can consider to enhance their guests' satisfaction and optimize their operations:

- Smart room features: Implementing smart room features such as voice-activated controls for lighting and temperature can enhance the guest experience and provide a modern touch to hotel rooms.

- Online reputation management: Monitoring online reviews and social media channels can provide valuable feedback about guest experiences and help hotels to improve service quality. Hotels can also respond to reviews and engage with guests on social media to build positive relationships and enhance their reputation.

- Automated inventory management: Implementing an automated inventory management system can streamline supply chain operations, reduce waste, and improve cost efficiency. The system can automatically track inventory levels and alert staff when supplies need to be replenished, reducing the risk of stockouts and overstocking.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the hotel industry in Turkey has made significant strides in recent years in terms of adopting digital technologies to enhance the guest experience and improve operational efficiency. This has helped to establish Turkey as a leading tourist destination, known for its high-quality hotel services and sustainable tourism practices. While the hotel industry in Uzbekistan is still catching up to Turkey in terms of digital service adoption, there is great potential for growth and development in the years ahead. By implementing digital service recommendations such as mobile check-in and check-out, in-room tablets, and digital concierge services, hotels in Uzbekistan can improve their guests' experience and remain competitive in a rapidly evolving market.

Overall, the hotel industry in both Turkey and Uzbekistan has an important role to play in developing sustainable tourism practices that promote economic growth, protect the environment, and preserve cultural heritage. By embracing digital technologies and focusing on guest satisfaction, hotels in both countries can contribute to a more sustainable and prosperous future for their communities and the wider tourism industry.

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